

Socioeconomic impact

Price difference of rice grades: case of parboiled and raw rice

M. Wileratne and T. L. L. Chandrakumara, Agricultural Economics Department, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Ruhuna, Kamburupitiya, Sri Lanka

We investigated the price differences between two major grades of rice: parboiled and raw. We collected retail rice prices during 1990 in the important rice-producing districts in Sri Lanka of Hambantota and Polonnaruwa. Monthly average prices were computed (see table).

Prices of parboiled rice were comparatively higher in Hambantota whereas prices of raw rice were higher in Polonnaruwa. Hambantota consumers prefer raw rice to parboiled rice.

Producers are disinclined to use parboiling techniques. Although this district is regarded as a surplus area, parboiled rice is not supplied through the marketing system.

Consumers in Polonnaruwa district prefer parboiled rice, so producers tend to use parboiling techniques. Raw rice production is minimal. This district is also regarded as a surplus area. Even though the demand is less, the comparative price of raw rice is higher than that of parboiled rice.

The study reveals that the rice marketing system in each district is geared to purchase the surplus of the main rice grade produced there, but is not concerned about the supply of the other grades preferred by district consumers. ■

Price difference between parboiled and raw rice, Hambantota and Polonnaruwa districts, Sri Lanka, 1990.

Month	Difference (\$/1 000 kg)			
	Hambantota		Polonnaruwa	
	Parboiled	Raw	Parboiled	Raw
Jan	305.47	259.28	228.09	254.04
Feb	294.52	227.61	230.09	273.80
Mar	270.71	210.23	234.04	263.80
Apr	259.76	221.66	220.23	241.90
May	255.95	219.04	226.42	230.47
Jun	286.71	283.80	217.14	240.00
Jul	289.52	279.76	219.04	252.38
Aug	289.61	284.52	273.80	273.80
Sep	293.00	290.46	283.09	286.09
Oct	299.61	297.61	297.61	309.52
Nov	328.57	318.33	306.42	313.57
Dec	349.28	343.33	321.42	345.23

Announcements

Rice dateline^a

15-17 Mar	France-IRRI Workplan Meeting. IRRI. Contact K. Lampe. IRRI.
1-2 Apr	ICAR-IRRI Workplan Meeting. New Delhi, India. Contact G.L. Denning/F.A. Bernardo, IRRI.
5-6 Apr	BRRRI-IRRI Collaborative Research and Training Workplan Review. Bangladesh. Contact J.L. McIntosh/G.L. Denning/F.A. Bernardo, IRRI.
8-13 Apr	Bhutan-IRRI Project Planning Meeting. Bhutan. Contact G.L. Denning, IRRI.
12-16 Apr	Second Workshop on Rice Supply and Demand Project. IRRI. Contact M. Hossain, IRRI.
18-20 May	Upland Rice Consortium Steering Committee Meeting. IRRI. Contact M. Arraudeau, IRRI.
31 May-25 Jun	Management of Training Centers Training Course. Bangkok, Thailand. Contact Asian Institute of Technology. GPO Box 2754, Bangkok 10501, Thailand.
1-6 Jun	International Network on Soil Fertility and Sustainable Rice Farming (INSURF) Site Visit and Planning Meeting. China. Contact E.L. Aragon, IRRI.

^aAddress for all IRRI contacts: International Rice Research Institute, P.O. Box 933, Manila 1099, Philippines. Fax: 632-2-8 18-2087

CIAT releases video

The International Center for Tropical Agriculture (CIAT) announces the release of a new video, *A fragile paradise: environmental challenge of tropical America*. Two sections of the video focus on rice research in Latin America. The 27 min 45 s video is available in English and Spanish.

Individuals may order VHS or Beta copies, in NTSC or PAL, for US\$21 (includes air mail postage) from the Communications Unit, CIAT, A.A. 6713, Cali, Colombia. Fax: 57-23-647243. The video is also available for television broadcast. ■

Call for news

Individuals, institutions, and organizations are invited to tell readers about upcoming events in rice research or related fields for the Rice Dateline. Send announcements to the Editor, IRRN, International Rice Research Institute. P.O. Box 933, Manila 1099, Philippines. ■